

Orchestration-Centric Management for Asset-as-a-Service Systems

Michail Dalgitsis*, Berend Gort*, Lazaros Liatsas*, Maria A. Serrano*,
Godfrey Kibalya*, Dionysis Xenakis†, Angelos Antonopoulos*

*Nearby Computing, Barcelona, Spain

{mdalgitsis, bgort, lliatsas, maria.serrano, gkibalya, aantonopoulos}@nearbycomputing.com

†National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece

nio@uoa.gr

Abstract—Asset-as-a-Service (AaaS) is emerging as a key paradigm in industrial servitization, enabling usage-based access to assets while shifting operational responsibility and risk to service providers. In such environments, management objectives are realized through orchestration decisions that determine how asset-related services are configured and adapted across edge–cloud infrastructures. Effective orchestration depends on three interdependent dimensions: i) reliable decision evidence that informs candidate orchestration actions; ii) admissible operational configurations that constrain the space of permissible actions; and iii) explainable model outputs and validation mechanisms that ensure actions can be understood and approved under operational constraints. However, existing approaches treat these elements mainly in isolation. In this paper, we introduce an orchestration-centric AaaS management model that integrates these dimensions within a closed-loop decision framework. In addition, we propose an evaluation methodology linking predictive accuracy, expected loss reduction and human-centric validation to orchestration outcomes.

Index Terms—AaaS, Digital Twins, XAI, Asset Health Management, Edge-Cloud Orchestration

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial servitization is increasingly shifting asset utilization from ownership-based models toward service-oriented access, where customers pay for usage or outcomes rather than for physical equipment. In this Asset-as-a-Service (AaaS) paradigm, *assets* refer to physical or cyber-physical systems (e.g., industrial machines) whose operational state evolves over time and may degrade. Service providers retain responsibility for asset availability, performance and maintenance, while also assuming the associated operational and economic risk [1], [2]. Unlike Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), where resources are virtual and largely stateless, AaaS involves failure-prone, stateful entities, making decisions dependent on asset condition and uncertainty. As a result, AaaS operation requires continuous management of distributed assets under uncertainty, with decisions directly affecting service quality, cost and contractual exposure.

In AaaS systems, management decisions are realized as orchestration actions across distributed edge-cloud infrastructures. These include where analytics are executed, how intensively assets are monitored and when maintenance is triggered, translating high-level policies and assessments into operational decisions. Effective orchestration in AaaS settings relies on

three elements: *decision evidence*, *operational constraints*, and *human validation*. Asset Health Management (AHM) estimates asset condition (e.g., degradation level and remaining useful life), while economic risk metrics such as Annualized Loss Expectancy (ALE) translate predicted failures into expected operational and financial impact. These signals inform candidate orchestration actions. At the same time, decisions must remain bounded by admissible configurations defined through policies encoding service-level objectives, cost limits and risk tolerance. Virtual Commissioning (VC), i.e., pre-deployment validation in simulation environments, provides design-time safety constraints and operational limits that restrict permissible runtime actions.

Since orchestration decisions affect both digital services and physical assets, they must be explainable and traceable. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) explains how health and risk predictions influence candidate actions, enabling human operators to approve or override decisions within operational time constraints [3]. Digital Twins (DTs) support this process by maintaining a synchronized runtime representation of asset state and operational context, grounding analytics and orchestration decisions in an up-to-date system view [4], [5].

Despite advances in AHM, economic risk assessment, XAI and lifecycle-support technologies (e.g., DTs and VC), existing approaches treat these elements largely in isolation. This limits their applicability to AaaS, where orchestration must jointly account for predictive uncertainty, economic impact and constrained operational decisions.

In this paper, we address this challenge by: i) identifying integration gaps in existing approaches; ii) introducing an orchestration-centric AaaS management model where asset health and risk jointly guide decision-making under constraints; and iii) defining an evaluation methodology that links predictive accuracy, expected loss reduction and human validation to orchestration outcomes.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the state of the art in VC, AHM, XAI, and risk-aware orchestration. Section III presents the proposed model and decision loop. Section IV defines the evaluation methodology in terms of accuracy, risk reduction and explainability. Section V concludes the paper.

II. STATE OF THE ART

This section reviews the state of the art relevant to orchestration-centric AaaS management. Rather than surveying each domain independently, we focus on how existing approaches contribute *decision inputs*, *constraints* and *validation mechanisms* for orchestration in distributed, asset-centric systems, and highlight the gaps that prevent their integration into a unified orchestration framework.

A. Asset Health Management as Orchestration-Relevant Evidence

AHM and prognostics provide signals for detecting degradation and estimating Remaining Useful Life (RUL). Recent work improves predictive performance under complex and non-stationary conditions, using deep learning and hybrid modeling [6]. Within orchestration-centric AaaS operation, these outputs should be interpreted as *evidence* that modulates management actions, rather than as final decisions.

Specifically, anomaly likelihoods, degradation trends and uncertainty estimates can trigger deeper analysis, increased monitoring intensity or maintenance planning. Nonetheless, many AHM frameworks remain decoupled from service-level decision logic, as they report health metrics, but do not explicitly connect them to operational choices, economic consequences or policy constraints. This weak coupling limits their utility in AaaS environments, where health predictions must directly inform risk-aware and policy-constrained orchestration decisions.

B. Risk-Aware Service Management and Orchestration

Edge-cloud orchestration enables dynamic placement and scaling of services under performance and cost constraints [7]. However, most approaches primarily optimize technical metrics (latency, throughput, resource utilization) without integrating asset health information or explicit economic risk objectives into decision-making. Although risk metrics such as Annualized Loss Expectancy (ALE) are well established in risk management, they are rarely incorporated into orchestration governance. Recent work on risk-aware scheduling incorporates uncertainty and failure likelihood, but often lacks integration with asset health analytics and human validation workflows, preventing end-to-end decision-making across prediction, risk assessment and action selection [8].

C. Virtual Commissioning as Design-Time Priors and Constraints

VC validates control logic and system behavior in simulated environments prior to deployment. Recent surveys highlight its benefits in reducing commissioning time and deployment risk in cyber-physical production systems [9]. VC typically yields artifacts such as expected behavior envelopes, timing constraints and simulated failure scenarios.

From an orchestration perspective, VC is most valuable as *design-time prior knowledge*. It can initialize policy constraints (e.g., admissible operating regimes, safety bounds, timing

requirements) and calibrate thresholds used during early operation. In AaaS settings, where service responsibilities remain with the provider, such priors reduce uncertainty during onboarding and provide guardrails for subsequent orchestration actions. However, existing VC toolchains often remain weakly connected to runtime management loops, while systematic mechanisms for translating VC artifacts into enforceable orchestration constraints within runtime decision loops are still limited.

D. XAI for Human-in-the-Loop Orchestration Validation

XAI has become increasingly important as AI-driven analytics are deployed in safety- and revenue-critical industrial settings. Recent work emphasizes human-centered evaluation, focusing on user understanding and decision performance rather than explanation quality in isolation [10]. In orchestration-centric AaaS settings, the primary role of XAI is to provide interpretable explanations of the health and risk model outputs that inform orchestration actions.

In practice, orchestration produces candidate actions (e.g., analytics relocation, monitoring escalation, intervention requests) that affect both digital services and physical asset operation. These actions must be justified to operators and service stakeholders, who may approve, modify, or reject them. A key gap in the literature is that many XAI evaluations do not reflect time-bounded, human-in-the-loop orchestration workflows, leaving open questions on how explanations should be structured to support rapid, decision-centric validation in orchestration workflows.

Overall, existing approaches address decision inputs, constraints and validation in isolation, but lack a unified framework that jointly integrates health evidence, economic risk, policy constraints and human validation into orchestration decisions.

III. EDGE-CLOUD ORCHESTRATION-CENTRIC ASSET-AS-A-SERVICE MANAGEMENT MODEL

This section introduces an AaaS management model, where edge-cloud orchestration acts as the core mechanism that configures and adapts asset-management services during operation. A summary of potential orchestrated cloud-native asset-management services is provided in Table I.

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed approach: asset health assessment and economic risk evaluation provide the main *decision evidence* that informs orchestration actions, policies and VC-derived *constraints* limit the space of admissible decisions, while XAI and DTs support *explainability and validation* by providing interpretable model outputs and contextual system state for time-bounded human oversight.

A. Scope of Orchestration in AaaS Operation

In AaaS environments, orchestration defines how the lifecycle of asset-management services (Table I) is managed over time. Rather than managing components in isolation, orchestration operates over *service configurations* (e.g., where analytics run, how frequently monitoring executes, what level

TABLE I
CLOUD-NATIVE ASSET-MANAGEMENT SERVICES AND THEIR EXECUTION CHARACTERISTICS THAT CAN BE ADAPTED BY THE ORCHESTRATOR (E.G., PLACEMENT, SCALING, AND EXECUTION MODE)

AaaS Service	Orchestration-relevant Characteristics
Health monitoring & diagnostics	Containerized analytics, scalable pipelines, event-driven triggers, deployable across distributed execution contexts
Prognostics & RUL estimation	Elastic compute, model versioning, batch/stream processing for long-horizon analysis
Risk & impact assessment	Stateless evaluation services, policy-driven invocation, centralized economic/risk models
Explainable decision support	On-demand explanation generation, provenance tracking, decision-rationale APIs for operator validation
Data aggregation & preprocessing	Stream processing, dynamic scaling, data-local filtering/feature extraction for bandwidth-aware operation

Fig. 1. Orchestration-centric AaaS management loop with evidence, constraints and human validation

of model fidelity is used, which intervention workflow is activated, etc.). These configurations are continuously revised as asset condition, operational context and risk posture evolve.

Hence, orchestration decisions cover both *digital adaptations* (e.g, service placement, scaling, migration, etc.) and *operational interventions* (e.g., maintenance triggers, operating-mode constraints, escalation to experts). It is worth noting that orchestration provides a unifying control mechanism that aligns service execution with AaaS objectives while keeping functional implementations modular and cloud-native.

B. Health- and Risk-Informed Candidate Action Selection

Within the proposed model, AHM outputs are treated as probabilistic decision evidence: anomaly probability, degradation rate and Remaining Useful Life (RUL) estimates (with uncertainty) inform whether the current configuration remains adequate or escalation is required. For instance, these signals can justify increasing monitoring intensity, switching to more accurate models or requesting deeper analysis.

Economic risk evaluation complements health analytics by translating predicted failure likelihoods into expected operational and financial impact. Risk metrics such as ALE support

comparing candidate orchestration actions in terms of expected loss reduction versus cost or disruption. In this way, health and risk jointly drive *candidate action selection*: orchestration proposes alternative configurations or interventions and prioritizes them according to expected risk reduction under resource and policy constraints.

C. Policies and Virtual Commissioning Constraints

Orchestration policies translate service-level objectives, cost constraints and risk tolerance into decision boundaries that determine admissible configurations. Instead of hard-coding individual actions, policies express constraints and priorities (e.g., latency bounds, maximum allowable downtime risk, monitoring budgets, escalation rules, etc.) that guide the candidate action selection.

This constraint layer is strengthened by VC that provides validated design-time knowledge about system behavior. Through pre-deployment simulation of control logic and operational scenarios, VC produces safety limits, timing requirements, admissible operating regions and expected behavior bounds. These artifacts can be formalized as policy constraints and embedded into orchestration rules, preventing unsafe or infeasible actions at runtime. In this way, VC bridges design-time validation and runtime orchestration by transforming simulation-derived guarantees into enforceable decision constraints.

D. XAI-Enabled Human Validation and Explainability

Since orchestration actions can affect both service outcomes and physical asset operation, they must be explainable and subject to human oversight. In our proposed model, XAI supports the *validation* of candidate actions by explaining the health and risk model outputs that inform orchestration decisions (Fig. 1). Explanations summarize the key evidence (e.g., degradation indicators, risk estimates and relevant constraints) that influenced the recommendation.

Human operators validate actions through time-bounded workflows (i.e., approve/modify/reject). Validation outcomes and rationale are logged to support auditing and continuous improvement (e.g., refining policies, calibrating risk models, updating analytics, etc.). This validation gate ensures that safety- and revenue-critical actions remain operationally feasible and trustworthy under real decision-time constraints.

IV. RISK AND EXPLAINABILITY METRICS FOR ORCHESTRATION-CENTRIC AAAS MANAGEMENT

This section defines the metrics and evaluation methodology used to assess orchestration-centric AaaS management. In the proposed model, asset health analytics, economic risk assessment and explainable decision support jointly inform orchestration decisions across the edge-cloud continuum. Evaluation therefore focuses on whether orchestration actions lead to improved operational outcomes by reducing expected loss, while remaining reliable and explainable under operational constraints.

A. Accuracy Metrics Supporting Orchestration Decisions

Asset health analytics provide the primary signals used to inform and adapt orchestration actions, such as relocating analytics, increasing monitoring frequency or initiating maintenance workflows. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is used to evaluate how prediction accuracy varies across orchestration configurations, linking model performance to deployment decisions. For a set of N predictions, MAE is defined as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{y}_i - y_i|, \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y}_i denotes the predicted value and y_i the observed ground truth.

In the orchestration-centric context, accuracy metrics are not evaluated in isolation. Instead, MAE is assessed across different execution contexts and deployment configurations to ensure the reliability of health signals that inform orchestration policies under varying edge-cloud placements.

B. Risk Metrics for Orchestration Outcomes

In AaaS systems, the effectiveness of orchestration is ultimately measured by its impact on operational and economic risk. ALE is adopted as the primary risk metric, capturing the expected financial loss associated with asset failures and service disruptions over a one-year period:

$$\text{ALE} = \text{ARO} \cdot \text{SLE}, \quad (2)$$

where $\text{ARO} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ denotes the annualized rate of occurrence (expected number of failure events per year) and $\text{SLE} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ denotes the single-loss expectancy (expected loss per event). The product yields $\text{ALE} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ in [currency/year], i.e., the expected annual loss under a stationary risk profile.

Within the proposed methodology, ALE functions as a policy evaluation criterion rather than a control signal. For each candidate orchestration action (e.g., relocating analytics, scaling monitoring services or triggering maintenance), the expected loss is estimated and compared against the baseline. Orchestration actions are selected when their expected reduction in ALE justifies their operational or computational cost, enabling economically grounded and risk-aware orchestration governance.

C. Explainability and Human Validation in Orchestration Decisions

Because orchestration actions directly affect asset operation and service quality, they must be explainable and subject to rapid human validation. Explainability is therefore evaluated in terms of operator understanding of the factors underlying orchestration decisions, rather than explanation fidelity alone.

Output understanding measures the extent to which operators correctly comprehend why a specific orchestration action is recommended, including the contributing health indicators, estimated risk impact and policy constraints. Understanding is assessed using task-based evaluation and reported as the percentage of correct responses across validation tasks, following human-centered XAI practices.

Validation time captures the elapsed time between presentation of an orchestration recommendation and operator approval, modification or rejection. This metric reflects the operational feasibility of human-in-the-loop orchestration under time constraints.

To support accountability and governance, *decision provenance* is also evaluated. Provenance records identify the health signals, risk estimates and policy rules that contributed to each orchestration decision, enabling auditability, post hoc analysis and continuous refinement of orchestration policies.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced an orchestration-centric AaaS management model that integrates asset health assessment, economic risk evaluation and human-in-the-loop validation within a unified decision framework. Specifically, i) health and risk metrics inform candidate actions, ii) orchestration policies and VC constraints bound admissible configurations, and iii) DT-driven explainable decision support enables human validation under operational constraints. An evaluation methodology was defined to assess orchestration outcomes in terms of predictive accuracy, expected loss reduction and validation performance. This provides a basis for systematically comparing alternative orchestration strategies in AaaS environments. Future work will focus on validating the proposed approach through simulation and real-world deployments across heterogeneous assets and operational settings.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the MSCA EC projects EXARCH (101236244) and ELIXIRION (101120135).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kolagar *et al.*, "Linking Digital Servitization and Industrial Sustainability Performance: A Configurational Perspective on Smart Solution Strategies," *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. 71, pp. 7743–7755, 2024.
- [2] Y. Xing *et al.*, "Servitization innovation: A systematic review, integrative framework, and future research directions," *Technovation*, vol. 122, p. 102641, 2023.
- [3] K. Kadi and L. El Abbadi, "INDUSTRY X.0: Technologies, Methods, and Sectoral Transformations," in *IEEE 8th CiSt*, 2025, pp. 626–630.
- [4] Y. Vittorakis *et al.*, "On the Resource Consumption of 2D Human Pose Estimation Services in MEC-enabled Networks," in *IEEE NFV-SDN*, 2025, pp. 1–6.
- [5] A. Sotiropoulos *et al.*, "On the Resource Consumption of XR-enabled Digital Twin Applications in the Edge-Cloud Continuum," in *IEEE NFV-SDN*, 2025, pp. 1–6.
- [6] T.-K. Nguyen *et al.*, "A Remaining Useful Lifetime Prediction Model for Concrete Structures using Mann-Whitney U Test State Indicator and Deep Learning," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 222, p. 111795, 2025.
- [7] L. Qi *et al.*, "A Novel Distributed Orchestration Engine for Time-Sensitive Robotic Service Orchestration Based on Cloud-Edge Collaboration," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 3943–3954, 2025.
- [8] P. Kokkinakis *et al.*, "Risk-Aware Resource Allocation in Edge Computing Using Stochastic Forecasting," in *IEEE ICC*, 2025, pp. 3648–3653.
- [9] N. Striffler and T. Voigt, "A 3D Approach for the Virtual Commissioning of Processing Plants," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 21 190–21 209, 2025.
- [10] S. S. Alhasan and R. A. Alnanih, "Enhancing AI Explainability Through the EXACT Framework: A User-Centric Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 98 208–98 228, 2025.